

Computational determination of preferred orientation of heteroepitaxial systems: Influence of elements selection and area size

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Epitaxy
Thin film
Crystallographic plane
Out-of-plane orientation
In-plane orientation

ABSTRACT

The atomic arrangement in the *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* adjacent planes allows to determine their preferred out-of-plane (OP) and in-plane (IP) orientation. The pair of *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* planes with the largest average number of mutual atomic overlaps corresponds to the preferred OP orientation. The highest value of the number of overlaps at a specific in-plane rotation angle of the substrate relative to the film corresponds to the preferred IP orientation. This is the structure compatibility calculation (SCC) method whose outputs were compared with experimentally determined OP and IP orientations for five *substrate/film* systems: *Ni/BN*, *GaN/FeN*, *MgO/ZnO*, *SrTiO₃/ZnO* and *Al₂MgO₄/ZnO*. The SCC included the experimentally determined *substrate(hkl)* plane and various densely occupied *film(hkl)* planes including those experimentally determined. The results proved that the elements selection from both planes has no effect on the 100 % accuracy of SCC in determining the OP orientation. This finding, in addition to the purely geometric approach, is important proof of simplicity and efficiency of the SCC. For IP orientation, ~93 % accuracy of SCC results was achieved. The elements selection has less influence on the determined IP orientation compared to area sizes of the *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* systems. Too small areas may make it impossible to determine the IP orientation using the SCC.

1. Introduction

Epitaxial thin films are crystalline materials with a thickness ranging from tenths to thousands of nanometers, and adjacent to the crystalline materials of the substrate [1]. At the interface, the atoms of both materials are interconnected via chemical bonds. A division into homoepitaxial (identical material of the film and substrate) and heteroepitaxial (different material of the film and substrate) systems has been established [2,3]. The heteroepitaxial category can be further divided according to the composition of the substrate/film system into oxide/oxide [4–8], non-metal/oxide [9], metalloid/oxide [10,11], sulfide/metal [12], fluoride/oxide [13], etc. Attention has also recently been paid to the synthesis of heteroepitaxial systems of the nitride/nitride [14], metal/nitride [15] or metalloid/nitride [16–18] type.

The synthesis of heteroepitaxial systems can be achieved, e.g. by molecular beam epitaxy [15], physical vapour deposition (magnetron sputtering [13,14,16,18], radio frequency sputtering [9], pulsed laser deposition [4,5]), chemical vapour deposition [7,11] or other methods (chemical bath deposition [6], sol-gel [8,10], etc.) for the purpose of their use in various practical applications – optoelectronic devices such

as UV nanolasers [5,11,18], optical waveguides [4,5], light emitting diodes [4–7,11,13,18], spintronic and memory storage devices [10,14] or hard coatings on cutting tools [17], to name a few.

The formation of chemical bonds between the atoms of the film and the substrate at their interface depends not only on the atoms present, but also on their mutual position, i.e. the planar geometry of the system. Two basic parameters are used to characterize this geometry: the out-of-plane (OP) orientation, i.e. which *substrate(hkl)* plane is adjacent and parallel to which *film(hkl)* plane, and the in-plane (IP) orientation, i.e. planar angle between two crystallographic directions, one of each *substrate(hkl)* and *film(hkl)* plane. While the OP orientation is usually evaluated by identifying (hkl) planes using X-ray diffraction analysis [4–18] or high-resolution transmission electron microscopy [8], the IP orientation is most often determined by off-axis phi scanning [4–7,14,15].

OP and IP can be determined computationally. A commonly used approach is based on lattice mismatch, i.e. the percentage difference in the length of the lattice parameters of two phases (e.g. substrate and film). In addition to the most commonly used one-dimensional lattice mismatch comparing only one lattice parameter of the film with one

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2025.107665>

Received 2 July 2025; Received in revised form 7 August 2025; Accepted 12 September 2025

Available online 13 September 2025

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lattice parameter of the substrate [4,5,7,17], more complex two-dimensional lattice mismatch is also used [19]. This method allows to determine the preferred OP orientation for a given *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* system using three directions in each crystallographic plane: two directions parallel to the lattice vectors *a* and *b*, a third direction between them. In each direction, the interatomic distance is determined. The angular differences between pairs of directions (i.e., those parallel to the *a* in substrate and plane, those parallel to the *b* in substrate and plane, and the third ones) are also determined. From each pair of directions, a partial lattice mismatch (formula) is calculated, and the average of these three values quantifies the OP orientation of a given *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* system.

An alternative approach is the "Structure Compatibility Calculation" (SCC) working with the number of overlaps of atoms of adjacent (hkl) planes of two crystallographic phases [20–22]. One (hkl) plane is rotated in-plane relative to the other, and the number of overlapping pairs of atoms, each atom from one (hkl) plane, is counted at each rotation step. The average number of overlaps from all rotation steps indicates the structure compatibility of these two (hkl) planes and by comparing it with the values for other (hkl) planes, the OP orientation is determined: the highest average number of overlaps corresponds to the most probable OP orientation.

The SCC approach was developed as a supporting tool for molecular modeling to select adjacent (hkl) planes (i.e. the OP orientations) in TiO₂ nanoparticle / SiO₂ substrate system which were subsequently used in a force field-based geometry optimization [20]. The results of the SCC (average number of overlaps for various TiO₂(hkl) and SiO₂(hkl) planes) and molecular modeling (strength of interaction between TiO₂ and SiO₂ oriented by given (hkl) planes) were in agreement: the higher the number of overlaps, the stronger the interaction. Although the SCC does not involve energy, similar to lattice mismatch methods, there is a connection between its results and the lowest potential energies (i.e., the strongest interactions). The formation of bonds between atoms of adjacent (hkl) planes is conditioned by similar positions of these atoms in space, which in a two-dimensional representation corresponds to overlaps. If the distribution of bonding atoms is similar in both (hkl) planes, such a system exhibits a stronger interaction (and lower potential) energy compared to a pair of (hkl) planes, where proximity of bonding atoms cannot be achieved due to the more different pattern of these atoms in the given (hkl) planes. This is expressed by the SCC as a higher number of overlaps in the first case and a lower number of overlaps in the second one.

Further research into the OP orientation of nanoparticle/substrate systems (ZnS on kaolinite) confirmed the agreement of SCC and molecular modeling results, as well as the agreement of both methods with the experimental determination of the OP orientation using transmission electron microscopy [21]. This was evidence that the OP orientation of nanoparticles on substrate can be determined directly using the SCC, without the need to use more time-consuming and computationally intensive molecular modeling [21]. It was also demonstrated that the ratio "number of overlaps / area of plane" converges with increasing area and that an area of 100 × 100 Å² is sufficient for determining the OP orientation [20,21].

Recently, the SCC approach was newly applied to heteroepitaxial systems (oxides, sulfides, metals) [22]. In addition to the determination of OP orientation, the possibility of determining the IP orientation via the highest number of overlaps from all rotation steps was also demonstrated [22]. Very good agreement with experimental data confirmed that even in the case of heteroepitaxial systems, the SCC alone is sufficient to determine OP and IP orientation [22]. It was also shown that the interatomic distance defining the overlap does not affect the accuracy of the determination of OP orientation [22]. Those atoms for which a bond or at least strong interaction can be expected were included in the SCC: O from substrates (e.g. MgO, SrTiO₃, Al₂MgO₄) and Zn from ZnO [22]. In the case of simple binary structures, interchanging elements has no effect on the SCC results due to the identical patterns

Table 1

List of compounds reported as substrates and films and their experimentally determined OP and IP orientations.

substrate	film	OP orientation	IP orientation	Ref.
Ni	BN	Ni(111) BN(001)	Ni[-110] BN[110]	[15]
GaN	FeN	GaN(001) FeN(111)	GaN[110] FeN[110]	[14]
MgO	ZnO	MgO(100) ZnO(001)	MgO[-140] ZnO[100]	[4]
SrTiO ₃	ZnO	SrTiO ₃ (100) ZnO(001)	SrTiO ₃ [110] ZnO[010]	[7]
SrTiO ₃	ZnO	SrTiO ₃ (200) ZnO(001)	SrTiO ₃ [110] ZnO[010]	[7]
Al ₂ MgO ₄	ZnO	Al ₂ MgO ₄ (111) ZnO(001)	Al ₂ MgO ₄ (-1-12) ZnO(110)	[6]

(the O pattern and the Zn pattern are identical in e.g. ZnO(100), ZnO(001) or ZnO(110), the Mg pattern and the O pattern are identical in e.g. MgO(100), MgO(110) or MgO(111), etc.). However, a different situation occurs, e.g. for SrTiO₃ or Al₂MgO₄ where the Sr+Ti pattern or Al+Mg pattern, respectively, does not match the O patterns. Also the patterns containing both metal and oxygen (Sr+O, Al+O, Zn+O, etc.) are different. Until now, it has not been investigated whether the choice of one element or a combination of more elements from a given *film(hkl)* plane and *substrate(hkl)* plane affects or does not affect the SCC outcome, i.e. the determination of OP and IP orientation. This study is therefore aimed at answering this question, using both oxide systems MgO/ZnO [4], SrTiO₃/ZnO [6] and Al₂MgO₄/ZnO [7] already studied using SCC [22] and nitride systems GaN/FeN [14] and Ni/BN [15] studied using SCC for the first time. Moreover, while the influence of film and substrate size on the determination of OP using SCC is already known [20, 21], this is not the case for IP. Therefore, the influence of film and substrate area size on IP determination using SCC on all the above systems is also investigated in this study.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Experimental data

OP and IP orientations of the real samples of heteroepitaxial systems were taken from a literature [4–7,14,15]. Substrates, films and orientations given as *substrate(hkl) || film(hkl)* or *substrate[hkl] || film[hkl]* are summarized in Table 1.

2.2. Structure compatibility calculation

Since the basic principles of the SCC method have been published previously [20–22], only a brief description follows. Two (hkl) planes are placed in one geometric plane so that one atom of each plane is located at the origin of the coordinates. A pair of atoms, each from one (hkl) plane, having a centre distance equal to or less than the specified value forms an overlap. The centre distance value was selected with respect to the covalent radii [23] of elements in the studied systems. Covalent radii (in Å) of the elements (0.66 (O), 0.71 (N), 0.84 (B), 1.21 (Al), 1.22 (Ga, Zn), 1.24 (Ni), 1.32 (Fe), 1.41 (Mg), 1.60 (Ti), 1.95 (Sr)) give average values of 0.93±0.23 (Ni/BN), 1.08±0.27 (GaN/FeN), 1.10±0.32 (MgO/ZnO), 1.13±0.28 (Al₂MgO₄/ZnO), and 1.36±0.48 (SrTiO₃/ZnO). The mean value of the intersection of all five intervals is 1.02 Å, which, after rounding to 1.00 Å, was used as the centre distance for all systems.

One (hkl) plane rotates in-plane relative to the other with a rotation step of 1°. The rotation axis perpendicular to the geometric plane passes through the origin of coordinates. The number of overlaps is determined at each rotation step. The structure compatibility of two (hkl) planes is expressed as the average number of overlaps over all 360 rotation steps. The OP orientation is determined by comparing these values for different (hkl) planes, with the highest value giving the OP orientation [20–22]. The IP orientation for a given OP orientation is determined by comparing the numbers of overlaps from each rotation step, with the highest value giving the IP orientation [22].

Table 2

Compounds and lattice parameters of unit cells.

compound	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	α (°)	β (°)	γ (°)	Ref.
BN	2.504	2.504	6.661	90	90	120	[25]
FeN	4.200	4.200	4.200	90	90	90	[26]
ZnO	3.249	3.249	5.205	90	90	120	[27]
Ni	3.524	3.524	3.524	90	90	90	[28]
GaN	3.180	3.180	5.166	90	90	120	[29]
MgO	4.211	4.211	4.211	90	90	90	[30]
SrTiO ₃	3.899	3.899	3.899	90	90	90	[31]
Al ₂ MgO ₄	8.080	8.080	8.080	90	90	90	[32]

Table 3

Films and their selected (hkl) planes.

film	(hkl) planes	Fig.
BN	(001), (100), (102), (112), (116)	1
FeN	(111), (110), (311), (100), (511), (211)	2
ZnO	(100), (001), (101), (102), (110), (103), (112)	3

An area of 100×100 Å was used in this study to determine the OP orientation. This area was proved sufficient for this purpose in previous studies [20,21]. Since the influence of area size on determination of IP orientation has not yet been described, the IP orientation was studied for seven areas (10×10 , 20×20 , 30×30 , 50×50 , 100×100 , 200×200 , 300×300 Å) so that the influence could be evaluated.

2.3. Preparation of 3D structures

Unit cells with lattice parameters corresponding to bulk structures (Table 2) for individual materials acting as a substrate (Ni [15], GaN [14], MgO [4], SrTiO₃ [7] and Al₂MgO₄ [6]) and as a thin film (BN [15], FeN [14] and ZnO [4,6,7]) were constructed in VESTA software [24]. For the original 3D structures, the reader is referred to the original data (see the Data Availability).

2.4. Selection of (hkl) planes and preparation of input data

All experimentally confirmed planes (Table 1) were included in the input data. Moreover, based on simulated X-ray diffraction (Bragg-Brentano geometry, $\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha} = 1.540$ Å) performed using the module Reflex in the Materials Studio software (Biovia) [33], (hkl) planes showing sufficiently high reflection intensity values (≥ 20 % of the intensity of the most intense reflection) were used for the preparation of films input data (Table 3; see also Page 1 in the Supplementary material 1). The exception was the BN exhibiting only one (hkl) plane with reflection meeting this condition: the most intense reflection of the BN(001) plane (see page 1 in the Supplementary material 1). In order to increase the number of planes, also the planes having reflections with intensities < 20 % of the maximum were taken into account (Table 3).

In the case of substrates, no simulated diffractograms were created. Only experimentally confirmed planes Ni(111), GaN(001), MgO(100), SrTiO₃(100), SrTiO₃(200), Al₂MgO₄(111) (Table 1) were used for the preparation of substrates input data. The (hkl) planes of the films and substrates are provided in Figs. 1–4 including crystallographic directions (as listed in Table 1) and interatomic distances.

Each input data file describing the distribution of atoms in a given (hkl) plane consists of at least one line with six Cartesian coordinates: position of the centre of given atom (X, Y), direction (dx1, dy1) of copying the atom to create a row, and direction (dx2, dy2) of copying an entire row. For more complex patterns, the input data file may contain more than one line of coordinates. Due to the periodicity of the atomic arrangement, these coordinates allow creating a given (hkl) plane of arbitrary dimensions.

The following notation of elements from the substrate(hkl) and film(hkl) planes was used. Elements selected from the substrate are listed first and separated by a dash from elements selected from the film. The element selected from a given plane is indicated by the element symbol, e.g. Ni from a Ni(111) substrate. If the patterns of different elements from the same plane are identical (e.g. B pattern and N pattern in BN) and the input data therefore represents both elements, the elements are separated by a slash, e.g. Ni–B/N means that Ni–B is identical to the Ni–N. When more than one element is selected from the substrate and/or

Fig. 1. Atom patterns in the (a) (001), (b) (100), (c) (102), (d) (112) and (e) (116) planes of the BN structure (B – green, N – gray). In (a) BN(001), the experimentally determined in-plane direction [110] is indicated.

Fig. 2. Atom patterns in the (a) (111), (b) (110), (c) (311), (d) (100) for both Fe and N exhibiting the same pattern, (e) (511) and (f) (211) planes of the FeN structure (Fe – brown, N – gray). For *FeN*(111) (a) experimentally determined in-plane direction [110] is indicated.

Fig. 3. Atom patterns in the (a) (100), (b) (001), (c) (101), (d) (102), (e) (110), (f) (103) and (g) (112) planes of the ZnO structure (O – red, Zn – gray). In (b) *ZnO* (001), the experimentally determined in-plane direction [100] and plane (100) are indicated.

Fig. 4. Patterns in substrate planes (a) $Ni(111)$, (b) $GaN(001)$ (Ga – green, N – grey), (c) $MgO(100)$ (Mg – orange, O – red), (d) $SrTiO_3(100)$, (e) $SrTiO_3(200)$ (Sr – green, Ti – turquoise, O – red). (f) $Al_2MgO_4(222)$, and (g) $Al_2MgO_4(111)$ (Al – blue, Mg – orange, O – red). For all substrate planes, the experimentally determined in-plane directions (a) $[-110]$, (b) $[110]$, (c) $[-140]$, (d,e) $[110]$ and (g,f) plane $(-1-12)$ are indicated.

Table 4

The studied systems $substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)$ and the tested combinations of selected elements.

substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)	tested combinations of selected elements
$Ni(111)/BN(hkl)$	Ni–B/N; Ni–BN
$GaN(001)/FeN(hkl)$	Ga/N–Fe/N; Ga–FeN; GaN–Fe/N, GaN–FeN
$MgO(100)/ZnO(hkl)$	Mg/O–Zn/O; Mg–ZnO; MgO–Zn, MgO–ZnO
$SrTiO_3(100)/ZnO(hkl)$	O–Zn/O; Ti–Zn/O; TiO–Zn/O; Ti–ZnO; TiO–ZnO
$SrTiO_3(200)/ZnO(hkl)$	Sr/O–Zn/O; SrO–Zn; Sr–ZnO; SrO–ZnO
$Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(hkl)$	O–Zn/O; Al/Mg–Zn/O; Al/Mg–ZnO; AlO/MgO–Zn/O; AlMg–Zn/O; AlMg–ZnO, AlO/MgO–ZnO
$Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(hkl)$	Al–Zn/O; Al–ZnO

film, the selected elements are written next to each other, e.g. Ga–FeN for only Ga from the GaN substrate and both Fe and N from the FeN film, or GaN–FeN for both Ga and N from the GaN substrate and both Fe and N from the FeN film. If a pair of elements from a given plane shows the same pattern as a pair of other elements from the same plane, e.g. AlO and MgO from $Al_2MgO_4(111)$, a slash between these pairs is also used, e.g. AlO/MgO–ZnO. All tested combinations are listed in Table 4, and all input data are provided in Supplementary material 1 (Page 2).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Out-of-plane orientations

To determine the OP orientations using SCC, a total of 179 $substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)$ pairs were tested: 10 $Ni(111)/BN(hkl)$, 22 $GaN(001)/FeN(hkl)$, 28 $MgO(100)/ZnO(hkl)$, 5 $SrTiO_3(100)/ZnO(hkl)$, 4 $SrTiO_3(200)/ZnO(hkl)$, 7 $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(hkl)$, and 2 $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(hkl)$ (Fig. 5). For all tested combinations of selected elements, the highest numbers of overlaps were found for $Ni(111)/BN(001)$ (Fig. 5a), $GaN(001)/FeN(111)$ (Fig. 5b), $MgO(100)/ZnO(001)$ (Fig. 5c), $SrTiO_3(100)/ZnO(001)$ and $SrTiO_3(200)/ZnO(001)$ (Fig. 5d), $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(001)$ (Fig. 5e) pairs. This is in perfect agreement with experiments (Table 1). The trend of average number of overlaps values is maintained for each combination of elements selected from $substrate(hkl)$ and $film(hkl)$ planes (Fig. 5). This finding demonstrates that the selection of elements does not affect the correct determination of OP using SCC. All OP data are provided in Supplementary material 1 (Page 3).

3.2. In-plane orientations

IP orientations were determined only for the OP orientations showing the highest number of overlaps, i.e. OP orientations consistent with the experiment as demonstrated in 3.1 section. In order to determine the effect of area size, SCC was performed for seven areas – 10×10 , 20×20 , 30×30 , 50×50 , 100×100 , 200×200 and $300 \times 300 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 5). The preferred IP orientation was determined as the rotation

Fig. 5. Average number of overlaps for selected elements in (a) $Ni(111)/BN(hkl)$, (b) $GaN(001)/FeN(hkl)$, (c) $MgO(100)/ZnO(hkl)$, (d) $SrTiO_3(100)/ZnO(hkl)$ and $SrTiO_3(200)/ZnO(hkl)$, (e) $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(hkl)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(hkl)$ systems. Since $FeN(100)$ does not contain both Fe and N, the combinations Ga–FeN and GaN–FeN have not been tested for this plane (see X in (b)).

angle at which the maximum number of overlaps was achieved, and the agreement with the experimentally confirmed IP orientation was evaluated (Table 1).

The results can be divided into the following three groups: perfect agreement (✓), agreement (✓), disagreement (×) (Table 5). The perfect agreement (✓) means that the rotation angles exhibiting the global maxima of the number of overlaps correspond to the experimentally confirmed IP orientation ($\pm 5^\circ$). Agreement (✓) means that the rotation angles exhibiting the local maxima of the number of overlaps correspond to the experimentally confirmed IP orientation ($\pm 5^\circ$). The maximum angular deviation of $\pm 5^\circ$ was determined based on the resulting data – specifically, it is present in a single case for $Ni(111)/BN(001)$ Ni–BN at an area of $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ (see Page 5 in Supplementary Material 1). In the remaining cases, the angular deviation is lower. It reaches values of $1\text{--}4^\circ$. Disagreement (×) means that no rotation angle exhibiting the global or local maximum of the number of overlaps corresponds to the experimentally confirmed IP orientation.

For the $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ area, a total of 20 agreements (19 of them perfect) and 8 disagreements were found (Table 5). The agreement rate of SCC with experiment was therefore relatively low (71.42 %) and such small areas are obviously not suitable for determining IP. Larger areas of $20 \times 20 \text{ \AA}$ and $30 \times 30 \text{ \AA}$ have already started to show much higher agreement rates – 26 agreements for $20 \times 20 \text{ \AA}$ (24 of them perfect) and only 2

disagreements, 27 agreements for $30 \times 30 \text{ \AA}$ (26 of them perfect) and only 1 disagreement (Table 5). The SCC method therefore exhibits agreement rates of 92.86 % and 96.43 % for these areas. The maximum agreement rate can be observed for the $50 \times 50 \text{ \AA}$ area – exactly 100 %, with all cases except one being in perfect agreement. For the $100 \times 100 \text{ \AA}$ area, agreement in IP orientation was found also in all 28 (24 of them perfect) cases (i.e. 100 % agreement rate). The relatively high agreement rate of the SCC method is evident for area of $200 \times 200 \text{ \AA}$, namely 25 agreements (19 of them perfect) and 3 disagreements, i.e. 89.29 % agreement rate (Table 5). All three disagreements were found for the $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(001)$ systems. At the largest area ($300 \times 300 \text{ \AA}$), a total of 28 agreements (23 of them perfect) and no disagreement were observed. If the unsuitable area of $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ is omitted, the total agreement rate for all other areas is 96.43 % (85.12 % is a perfect agreement).

Due to the occurrence of several disagreements obtained for $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(001)$ at an area of $200 \times 200 \text{ \AA}$ (Tables 5 and 6), an additional SCC was performed for these systems with a centre distance of 1.1 \AA (average of Al, Mg, Zn and O covalent radii, see Section 2.2). The determination of the IP orientation under these conditions was significantly more successful for the area of $200 \times 200 \text{ \AA}$: all three disagreements obtained using a centre distance of 1 \AA turned to agreements, and all agreements turned to perfect

Table 5

Perfect agreement (✓), agreement (✓) or disagreement (×) with the experimentally confirmed IP orientations for the studied systems in dependence of selected atoms, area sizes, and centre distance of 1 Å. Original data are provided in the supplementary materials 1 (Page 5) and 2. agreement rates, i.e. percentage of ✓ and ✓ for the given area size, are listed in the last row. For Al_2MgO_4/ZnO systems, the results obtained using centre distance of 1.1 Å are in parentheses.

area size (nm ²)							
selected atoms	1	4	9	25	100	400	900
Ni(111)/BN(001)							
Ni-B/N	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ni-BN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GaN(001)/FeN(111)							
Ga/N-Fe/N	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ga-FeN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GaN-Fe/N	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GaN-FeN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MgO(001)/ZnO(001)							
Mg/O-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mg/O-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MgO-Zn/O	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MgO-ZnO	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SrTiO ₃ (100)/ZnO(001)							
O-Zn/O	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ti-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
TiO-Zn/O	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ti-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
TiO-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SrTiO ₃ (200)/ZnO(001)							
Sr/O-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SrO-Zn/O	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sr/O-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SrO-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Al ₂ MgO ₄ (111)/ZnO(001)							
O-Zn/O	×	×	×	✓(×)	✓(✓)	✓(✓)	✓
Al/Mg-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×(✓)	✓
Al/Mg-ZnO	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓(✓)	✓(✓)
AlO/MgO-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓(✓)	✓
AlO/MgO-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓(✓)	✓
AlMg-Zn/O	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
AlMg-ZnO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Al ₂ MgO ₄ (222)/ZnO(001)							
Al-Zn/O	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	×(✓)	✓
Al-ZnO	✓(×)	✓	✓	✓	✓	×(✓)	✓
agreement rate (%)	71(68)	93	96	100(96)	100	89(100)	100

agreements (see the results in parentheses in Tables 5 and 6). The agreement rate thus changed from 89 % to 100 %. On the contrary, a worsening is observed at smaller areas of 10×10 Å (✓ → ×) for Al-ZnO, and 50×50 Å (✓ → ×) and 100×100 Å (✓ → ✓) for O-Zn/O (see Tables 5 and 6). In the case of 10×10 Å, the worsening can be attributed to the small size of the area, as mentioned before. Nevertheless, if a centre distance of 1.1 Å is used for the $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(001)$ systems, the total agreement rate for all areas of all systems (except for the 10×10 Å) increases to 97.62 % (86.31 % is a perfect agreement).

Based on the agreement rates provided in the last row of the Table 5, the SCC method is most effective for 50×50 , 100×100 , 200×200 , and 300×300 Å sizes (Table 5). In the last two cases, however, the calculation time is longer. It can be stated that out of a total of 196 results, perfect agreement, agreement, and disagreement was found in 162, 20, and 14 cases, respectively, for a centre distance of 1 Å. Therefore, determination of IP orientation was unsuccessful in only 7.14 % of cases. For 82.65 % of cases, the IP orientation determined using SCC was in perfect agreement with the experiment. When the centre distance of 1.1 Å is involved (see the parentheses in Table 5), 163 perfect agreements, 20 agreements, and 13 disagreements are obtained, corresponding to unsuccessful determination and perfect agreement in 6.63 % and 83.16 % of cases, respectively.

For all three groups, it was also recorded what percentage of the global maximum the given local maximum reached (Table 6). The values of 1.00 correspond to the perfect agreement, and values in the range of 0.99–0.95 correspond to the agreement (i.e. ≥ 95 % limit). The lowest value in this group (95 %) was found in the case of $SrTiO_3(100)/$

$ZnO(001)$ for selected elements SrTi-ZnO (Pages 4 and 5 in the Supplementary material 1). Values below the 95 % limit correspond to disagreement. In this case, the lowest ratios were usually found for the smallest areas 10×10 Å. The results for the $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ and $Al_2MgO_4(222)/ZnO(001)$ systems when the centre distance value is changed to 1.1 Å are also included in Table 6.

Average value of all N_{IP}/N_{max} ratios is 0.990 ± 0.034 (Table 7). All results obtained by the SCC therefore differ from the ideal value of 1.000 only by a few hundredths. Specific values for individual systems range from 0.978 to 1.000 (Table 7). A relatively high value of 0.883 ± 0.060 was calculated even for disagreement category. These results demonstrate the reliability of SCC for determining the IP orientation of the studied systems.

For a more detailed description of IP orientations, the best and the worst systems according to the agreement with experimental data are discussed: the $Ni(111)/BN(001)$ with selected elements Ni-B/N, having perfect agreements at all seven surfaces, and the $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ with selected elements O-Zn/O, having agreements only at four surfaces (50×50 Å and higher). Attention was paid to their dependence of the number of overlaps on the rotation angle at the smallest (10×10 Å), middle (100×100 Å) and the largest (300×300 Å) area (Figs. 6, 7). For the $Ni(111)/BN(001)$ system with selected elements Ni-B/N, the experimentally determined IP orientation $Ni[-110]||BN[110]$ (Table 1) corresponds to a total of six rotation angles of $BN(001)$ film (Fig. 4a) relative to $Ni(111)$ substrate (Fig. 1a): 0° , 60° , 120° , 180° , 240° , 300° . The individual angle pairs ($0^\circ/180^\circ$, $60^\circ/240^\circ$, $120^\circ/300^\circ$) correspond to three mutual orientations of the $Ni[-110]$ and $BN[110]$ directions at the initial position of the crystallographic planes (Figs. 1a, 4a). Global or

Table 6

Ratios of the number of overlaps at experimentally confirmed IP angles to the maximum number of overlaps (N_{IP}/N_{max}) for perfect agreement (bold), agreement (unformatted) or disagreement (italics) for the studied systems in dependence of selected atoms, area sizes, and centre distance of 1 Å. original data are provided in the supplementary materials 1 (Page 5) and 2. agreement rates, i.e. percentage of perfect agreements and agreements for the given area size, are listed in the last row. For Al_2MgO_4/ZnO systems, the results obtained using centre distance of 1.1 Å are in parentheses.

area size (nm ²)	1	4	9	25	100	400	900
selected atoms							
Ni(111)/BN(001)							
Ni-B/N	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ni-BN	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
GaN(001)/FeN(111)							
Ga-N-Fe/N	1.00	<i>0.89</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ga-FeN	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00
GaN-Fe/N	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	0.98
GaN-FeN	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.99
MgO(001)/ZnO(001)							
Mg/O-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00
Mg/O-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00
MgO-Zn/O	<i>0.70</i>	<i>0.97</i>	1.00	0.98	0.97	1.00	1.00
MgO-ZnO	<i>0.88</i>	0.99	0.96	1.00	0.97	1.00	1.00
SrTiO ₃ (100)/ZnO(001)							
O-Zn/O	<i>0.91</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ti-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
TiO-Zn/O	<i>0.92</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ti-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
TiO-ZnO	0.95	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
SrTiO ₃ (200)/ZnO(001)							
Sr/O-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
SrO-Zn/O	<i>0.91</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sr/O-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
SrO-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Al ₂ MgO ₄ (111)/ZnO(001)							
O-Zn/O	<i>0.86(0.46)</i>	<i>0.92(0.84)</i>	<i>0.93</i>	1.00(0.92)	1.00(0.98)	0.98(1.00)	0.99
Al/Mg-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.88(0.99)	1.00
Al/Mg-ZnO	<i>0.83(0.71)</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99(1.00)	0.99(1.00)
AlO/MgO-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98(1.00)	0.99
AlO/MgO-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
AlMg-Zn/O	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
AlMg-ZnO	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Al ₂ MgO ₄ (222)/ZnO(001)							
Al-Zn/O	<i>0.88(0.89)</i>	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.93(0.98)	1.00
Al-ZnO	1.00(0.94)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.93(0.97)	1.00
agreement rate (%)	71(68)	93	96	100(96)	100	89(100)	100

Table 7

Average values of ratio of the number of overlaps at experimentally confirmed IP angles and the maximum number of overlaps ($(N_{IP}/N_{max})_{AVG}$) with standard deviations (SD) for individual categories of results. In the case of SrTiO₃ and Al₂MgO₄, the planes (100) with (200) and (111) with (222), respectively, are taken together for the calculation. The value in parentheses for Al₂MgO₄/ZnO category correspond to centre distance of 1.1 Å.

category of results	$(N_{IP}/N_{max})_{AVG} \pm SD (-)$
all results	0.990 ± 0.034
perfect agreement	1.000 ± 0.000
agreement	0.981 ± 0.011
disagreement	0.883 ± 0.060
Ni(111)/BN(001)	1.000 ± 0.000
GaN(001)/FeN(111)	0.994 ± 0.020
MgO(001)/ZnO(001)	0.978 ± 0.059
SrTiO ₃ (100) and (200)/ZnO(001)	0.995 ± 0.020
Al ₂ MgO ₄ (111) and (200)/ZnO(001)	0.986 ± 0.038 (0.978 ± 0.080)

local maxima for the dependence of the number of overlaps on the rotation angle were identified (exactly or with a maximum deviation of 4°) for all areas (Table 5).

The specific identification of overlaps is shown for areas 300 × 300, 100 × 100 and 10 × 10 Å (Fig. 6a-c). For the area of 300 × 300 Å (Fig. 6a), a deviation of 1° is observed for all six found maxima. The angle pair 179°/359° (or 0°/180° if the deviation is neglected)

corresponds to the global maximum. The remaining two pairs 59°/239° and 119°/299° (or 60°/240° and 120°/300° if the deviation is neglected) are local maxima and their overlap values are 99.5 % and 99.2 % of the global maximum. The exact angle values were identified for an area of 100 × 100 Å (Fig. 6b). There are four global maxima (0°/180° and 60°/240°). The remaining pair 120°/300° corresponds to a local maximum (96.7 % of the global maximum). At an area of 10 × 10 Å (Fig. 6c) global maxima were observed for all six experimentally determined rotation angles. The deviation 4° was found. Due to the small area size, the interval of numbers of overlaps was significantly narrowed to 7–21. In general, such a narrowing for a significant number of tested *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* systems made it difficult or impossible to predict the preferred IP orientation.

For the Al₂MgO₄(111)/ZnO(001) system with selected elements O-Zn/O, the experimentally determined IP orientation Al₂MgO₄(-1-12)||ZnO(110) (Table 1) corresponds to a total of six rotation angles of ZnO(001) film (Fig. 3b) relative to either Al₂MgO₄(111) (Fig. 4g) or Al₂MgO₄(222) substrate (Fig. 4f): 30°, 90°, 150°, 210°, 270°, 330°. The individual angle pairs (30°/210°, 90°/270°, 150°/330°) correspond to three mutual orientations of the IP planes Al₂MgO₄(-1-12) and ZnO(110) at the initial positions (Figs. 3b, 4g,f). Global or local maxima for the dependence of the number of overlaps on the rotation angle were identified (within a tolerance >95 % of the global maximum). At smaller areas (10 × 10 – 30 × 30 Å) this local maxima were <95 % (Table 5). The specific identification of overlaps is

Fig. 6. Dependencies of the number of overlaps on the rotation angle (step 1°) with marked maxima (red) corresponding to angles of experimentally confirmed IP orientation of the *Ni(111)/BN(001)* system for selected elements Ni–B/N together with their visualization at rotation angles of maximum values of their number of overlaps for areas (a) $300 \times 300 \text{ \AA}$ (59° , perfect agreement), (b) $100 \times 100 \text{ \AA}$ (0° , perfect agreement) and (c) $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ (4° , perfect agreement). colours in visualizations: green – non overlapping Ni atoms in *Ni(111)* plane, blue – non overlapping N or B atoms in *BN(001)* plane, red – overlapping Ni atoms in *Ni(111)* plane, black – overlapping B or N atoms in *BN(001)* plane.

shown for 300×300 , 100×100 and $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ areas (Fig. 7a-c). At an area of $300 \times 300 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 7a), four angles (30° , 150° , 210° , 330°) are observed as local maxima corresponding to 99.5 % (30° and 210°) and 99.4 % (150° and 330°) of the global maximum. The angle pair $90^\circ/270^\circ$ is already in a dense band of many other values and is therefore no

longer considered a local maximum. The exact values of the angles were identified at area of $100 \times 100 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 7b). Four angles this time correspond to the global maximum ($30^\circ/210^\circ$ and $150^\circ/330^\circ$) with 511 overlaps. The remaining pair $90^\circ/270^\circ$ corresponds to a local maximum (99 % of the global maximum). At an area of $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ (Fig. 7c), no

Fig. 7. Dependencies of the number of overlaps on the rotation angle (step 1°) with marked maxima and non-maxima (red) corresponding to angles of experimentally confirmed IP orientation of the $Al_2MgO_4(111)/ZnO(001)$ system for selected elements O-Zn/O together with their visualization at rotation angles of maximum values of their number of overlaps for areas (a) $300 \times 300 \text{ \AA}$ (6° , agreement), (b) $100 \times 100 \text{ \AA}$ (30° , perfect agreement) and (c) $10 \times 10 \text{ \AA}$ (1° , disagreement). Colours in visualizations: green – non overlapping O atoms in $Al_2MgO_4(111)$ plane, blue – non overlapping Zn atoms in $ZnO(001)$ plane, red – overlapping O atoms in $Al_2MgO_4(111)$ plane, black – overlapping Zn atoms in $ZnO(001)$ plane.

global maxima were observed for any of the six rotation angles. Due to the small area size, the interval of numbers of overlaps was significantly narrowed to 2–7. These low values made it impossible to include angles in the tolerance at any value of the number of overlaps lower than 7. It is necessary to state again that such a narrowing made it difficult or

impossible to predict the preferred IP orientation.

4. Conclusion

Using the SCC method, the OP and IP preferred orientations of a total

of five heteroepitaxial substrate/film systems (Ni/BN, GaN/FeN, MgO/ZnO, SrTiO₃/ZnO, and Al₂MgO₄/ZnO) were determined. The OP orientations (the highest average number of overlaps for given pair of (hkl) planes) are in absolute agreement with experimental data from the literature – namely Ni(111)/BN(001), GaN(001)/FeN(111), MgO(100)/ZnO(001), SrTiO₃(100)/ZnO(001), SrTiO₃(200)/ZnO(001), Al₂MgO₄(111)/ZnO(001) and Al₂MgO₄(222)/ZnO(001). The agreement with experiments was achieved in all cases studied regardless of the selected elements. Any selection of elements, one or more from one and/or the other (hkl) plane or from both (hkl) planes, results in the same trend of the average numbers of overlaps and thus leads to an equally correct determination of the OP orientation in agreement with the experiment. The absence of effect of the elements selection on the correct determination of the preferred OP orientation proves the useful simplicity of the SCC method.

The preferred IP orientation of the studied heteroepitaxial systems (the dependence of the number of overlaps on the in-plane rotation angle at the chosen area size) was also in agreement with experimental data from the literature – namely Ni[−110] || BN[110], GaN[110] || FeN[110], MgO[−140] || ZnO[100], SrTiO₃[110] || ZnO[010] and Al₂MgO₄(−1−12) || ZnO(110) for the corresponding preferred OP orientations of the studied systems. For centre distance of 1 Å, the agreement rate of determining the preferred IP orientation was 92.86 %, while 82.65 % of the results were in the perfect agreement with the experiment (92.86 % and 83.16 %, respectively, when centre distance of 1.1 Å is used for Al₂MgO₄/ZnO systems).

It was also demonstrated that the area size has a significant effect on the correct determination of the preferred IP orientation – with decreasing area size, the difficulty and ambiguity of accurately determining the preferred IP orientation increases (the most notably for 10 × 10 Å). On the contrary, for the large areas of 200 × 200 Å and 300 × 300 Å, reliable and accurate determination is limited by the more time-consuming calculations. In conclusion, the area size has a considerable effect on determining the preferred IP orientation, and areas of size 50 × 50 Å and 100 × 100 Å proved to be an ideal compromise.

Variations in results for Al₂MgO₄/ZnO systems when different centre distances are used demonstrate the sensitivity of IP orientation determination to the centre distance value, which should reflect the covalent radii of the selected elements. It was shown that the lower agreements of SCC results with experimental data for Al₂MgO₄(111)/ZnO(001) and Al₂MgO₄(222)/ZnO(001) at an area of 200 × 200 Å and centre distance of 1 Å were improved by using a value of 1.1 Å, which is closer to the covalent radii of Al, Mg, O, and Zn atoms. This adjustment yielded two uniform area size intervals with worse (10 × 10 Å – 40 × 40 Å) and better (50 × 50 Å – 300 × 300 Å) agreement rates. However, the original value of 1 Å proved to be suitable for most of the studied systems regardless of the area size (except for the too small and therefore unsuitable area of 10 × 10 Å) and the selection of elements.

The results obtained in this study demonstrate the simplicity, efficiency, and reliability of the SCC method for determining both the preferred OP and IP orientation of heteroepitaxial systems. Lattice mismatch methods are sufficient for simpler atomic patterns with a small number of atoms in the cell. The small number of atoms limits the number of possible directions for which the lattice mismatch is calculated (1 direction or 3 directions for 1D or 2D lattice mismatch, respectively). For more complex patterns with a larger number of atoms in the cell, the lattice mismatch is insufficient due to a higher number of possible directions, not all of which are included in the calculation of either 1D or 2D lattice mismatch. Inclusion of all atoms and directions, on the other hand, is a fundamental feature of the SCC method working with the entire surface of the *substrate(hkl)/film(hkl)* interface.

In addition to the preferred OP orientation, our SCC method simultaneously calculates the IP orientations (in fact, the OP orientation is determined as the average of all IP orientations), from which the preferred one is subsequently selected. Moreover, the SCC method allows visualization of the resulting overlaps at any chosen rotation angle.

This allows direct observation of the geometric distribution of the overlaps (i.e. whether they are randomly distributed or whether they form bands, circular or hexagonal regions, etc.).

Last but not least, it is important to note that the results were obtained using atomic arrangements based on the structural data of bulk materials. Further research will therefore be devoted mainly to the effect of interatomic lattice strain on the SCC results.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jonáš Molek: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jonáš Tokarský:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by The Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic from the projects SGS - Grant Agency of the VŠB-TUO (grant no SP2024/041, grant no SP2025/029), MATUR - Materials and Technologies for Sustainable Development (grant no CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.surfin.2025.107665](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2025.107665).

Data availability

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17106596>.

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